

topAM BRIEFING

Developing ODS high temperature alloys tailored for AM

The topAM Briefing covers project results from the last 6 months including:

- modelling the optimal dispersoid compositions and distributions
- AM production of samples and post-processing
- testing of the alloys in aggressive environments

Each work package is highlighted in a technical activity summary.

Follow the latest topAM project activities on LinkedIn (topAM Project) and Twitter (@topAMproject)! Also, the project website is regularly updated at <https://www.aspire2050.eu/TopAM>.

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WP2 Optimal computational design for LPBF based on ICME

An ICME framework for creep property modelling has been established based on VDM alloy 699XA (Figure 1). The framework incorporates mechanistic models (precipitation simulation, cavitation nucleation and growth, etc.) that describe process-induced microstructures and the resulting creep property based on the Dyson creep model. The model parameters have been calibrated against the

experimental results of VDM alloy 699XA which was heat treated and subjected to various characterization and testing techniques (EBSD, TEM, SYXRD, creep and tensile testing). With these models combined, the creep modelling framework enables the prediction of the creep life of the alloys at different temperatures and stress levels.

Figure 1. Creep modelling framework implemented for VDM alloy 699XA.

WP3 LPBF component design

Following the successful FBG sensor integration into the designed sensor channels considering metal additive manufacturing constraints, a drift measurement experiment was performed for finding the stability of the sensor measurement. A gold-coated high temperature FBG sensor was integrated within the gas burner head (shown in Fig 2 left) and a thermocouple was attached to the outer surface at

nearly the same location. The burner head was placed inside an oven at 800°C for 20 hrs and temperature measurements were compared from the sensor and the thermocouple (Fig 2 middle & right). It was observed that the FBG sensor can successfully survive the high temperature and overall showed very low drift (0.5°C/hr) during the experiment.

Figure 2. FBG sensor integration in a gas burner head with thermocouple (left); temperature measurements over the duration of the experiment (middle); Zoomed view of the temperature measurement comparison (right).

WP4 Powder production and modification

Work on the different powder modification routes has progressed and the status of each method is as follows:

- **Freeze Granulation (FG):** since the overall printability of FG powders turned out to be poor, the current work of RISE is focusing on alternative processing routes.
- **Mechanical Decoration/Alloying:** ZOZ has focused on mechanical decoration (low energy ball milling), as opposed to mechanical alloying (high energy ball milling) which resulted in non-flowable powders. Test batches of alloy 400 and alloy 699 have been decorated with 0.5 – 3vol.% of yttria.

The size distributions and shapes of the mechanically decorated powders are equal to the untreated powders (Figure 3). Currently the combination of decoration with subsequent alloying (short milling time only) is also being assessed.

- **Internal Oxidation/Nitridation:** the test batches on internal nitridation for alloy 699XA + Ti revealed a dissolved nitrogen content of ~ 1340 ppm for the in-situ process during atomization at INDUTHERM. Confirmation of successful titanium nitride formation is still underway. Work on internal oxidation is still in progress for the different alloys.

Figure 3. SEM-Image of SAC-MD-699 (left) with nano-Y₂O₃ adhered to the surface of the powder. Particle size distribution of alloys 400 and 699XA after mechanical decoration of 2 hours with 0.5wt% Y₂O₃ (right).

WP5 LPBF and Post-Processing

The development of LPBF process parameters is currently underway for all of the modified powders received from WP4. Overall, good processability has been observed in the alloys modified by internal oxidation/nitridation. In the case of alloy 400, further printing will be conducted to achieve even higher densities for the modified powders. The next step involves printing modified alloy 400 with high Zr content after in situ internal oxidation. For VDM alloy

699XA, the new powder from the mechanical decoration route containing 0.5% Y₂O₃ was successfully processed and showed promising results compared to the previous batch containing a higher amount of Y₂O₃. While internal oxidation modified 699XA exhibited good printability, the printed sample displayed cracks (Figure 4). The maximum densities achieved were 99.98% for the standard 699XA and 98.24% for the modified alloy composition.

MAC-PIO-699

- Good printability
- **Appearance of cracking with in every sample**
- Cracking leads to reduced optical density
- Density: 98,24 %

SAC-PIO-699

- Good printability
- Density: 99,98 %

Figure 4. The LPBF-processed modified (MAC) and unmodified (SAC) alloy 699, along with corresponding metallographic cross-sections.

WP6 Material properties

The screening tests of the cast/wrought and AM materials have been successfully accomplished, which means that milestone (MS7) is complete. The relevant information from those initial results are being compared with the target performance indicators (TPIs). The thermophysical property outcomes and microstructures are being collated and compared. As expected from the early AM microstructure analysis,

internal oxidation was observed to a varying extent after exposure in all atmospheres (air, H₂O, CO/H₂/H₂O and molten nitrates) for AM 699XA. The extent of internal oxidation was directly correlated to temperature. An Al slurry coating by LRUniv on alloy 699XA prevented internal oxidation by formation of an Al₂O₃ protective oxide layer on the surface.

Figure 7. (Left), uncoated; (right) Al-coated 699XA alloy oxidized at 1100°C/500h/air.

WP7 Proof of principle

Planning for the proof of principle validation at the end of the project is already underway, including the LPBF builds and the testing facilities for each condition. The

majority of these activities are scheduled for later in the project after the major results of the other WPs have been compiled.